

ASSESSING STUDENTS' UNDERSTANDING OF ACID-BASE CHEMISTRY IN GENERAL
CHEMISTRY

by

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Assessing Students' Understanding of Acid-Base Chemistry in General Chemistry

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Abstract

General Chemistry serves as a standard basis for more advanced chemistry courses, such as organic and analytical chemistry. For this reason, it is essential for students to understand the concepts taught in the General Chemistry course that will be carried and incorporated in future courses. Of the different topics covered, this study focuses on acid-base concepts. The purpose of this research was to assess students' ability to think abstractly when responding to conceptual questions about acid-base concepts and determining which teaching methods are most effective in the classroom. Cognitive dissonance is a psychological factor that hinders the learning of new concepts based on misconceptions from prior knowledge. To find these common misconceptions, students were given a pre and post assessment of questions about subtopics in the context of acids and bases; the pre-assessment was given before lecture to determine what the students already knew, and the post-assessment was given after lecture to determine how well the students understood the content. Results show that students struggle most with molecular representations of acid-base reactions. The approach in this study promotes critical thinking and shows instructors the common misconceptions in this course that can be taught in more detail for future students.

Introduction

General Chemistry is the fundamental building block that makes up higher level chemistry courses, such as organic and analytical chemistry. For this reason, it is important for students to be able to understand concepts taught in the general chemistry course to be able to carry them into future courses. Acid-base chemistry is one of the most difficult concepts taught in the general chemistry course¹. This topic in the general chemistry course consists of the following subtopics: titrations, pH, buffers, strength of acid and bases, and the equivalence point.

Statistically, 25% of undergraduate students who take general chemistry end up failing the course¹. The subject of acid-base chemistry requires conceptual understanding, such as what it means to which is why it is usually difficult for students to grasp the material. Students are usually taught these concepts briefly during high school, which are then expanded on in college. Their prior knowledge and difficulty with understanding certain concepts from high school conflicts with new knowledge and creates misconceptions². Misconceptions are difficult to tackle and eliminate because they are deeply rooted in the students' minds. This is known as cognitive dissonance, which is a psychological process where misconceptions arise because students find it difficult to make a connection between new concepts and prior knowledge³. Studies have shown that students in a classroom have common misconceptions, even if they acquired their prior knowledge from different places³. It is important to find effective teaching and learning methods to fix this contradiction between prior knowledge and new knowledge.

It is important to identify effective methods of learning that actively engage students in the classroom, which will help them understand the material on an abstract level. Acid-base chemistry requires abstract thinking when describing the interactions between substances on a particulate level, which is why it is important to have a teaching method that gets students to think on a conceptual level rather than being presented with possible choices to select the correct answer³. When students are given multiple choice exams, they find the correct answer by chance and often struggle with explaining why that is the correct answer, and that is because students tend to memorize certain ideas without regard to the scientific context, which results in misconceptions⁶. Multiple choice exams only allow students to rule out the incorrect options but do not get the students thinking about the (conceptual) reason why that is the answer. For example, students can memorize that a buffer resists a change in pH, but they usually cannot explain how a buffer works⁶. The term pH is also used to describe acidity and basicity but students do not really understand the concept of pH⁵. With a more hands-on and active approach in the classroom, students can get a better understanding of the scientific context of these topics.

The objective of this research is to probe students' common misconceptions in acid-base chemistry to determine effective learning strategies that eliminate these misconceptions and improve student learning in the classroom. In order to achieve this, pre and post questionnaires with conceptual free response questions were distributed in a general chemistry course, at the beginning and the end of the semester, to find common misconceptions in the students' responses. Since students seem to struggle most with identifying the reasons behind each concept, it can be hypothesized that students struggle most with describing what happens to molecules on a particulate level. It can be predicted that having students work in groups and explain to each other the correct answers to a worksheet is the most effective method of learning because it allows them to describe what they have learned and see whether they have understood the content.

Materials and Methods

In this study, a pre-assessment, or pre-test, and post-assessment, or post-test, with free response questions were distributed, as shown in Appendix 1. This type of questionnaire was handed out so that professors could see where students had common misconceptions and emphasize those concepts more while teaching. Multiple choice questions were not given because, with these types of questions, students would simply select the answer that seems correct from the options given without knowing the reason why that is the correct answer. This study was done with 24 students in the General Chemistry course, Chem120B, in the Spring semester of 2019.

Chem 120A pre-test

The pre-test was distributed at the beginning of the course to test what the students already knew coming into the course. The questions contained concepts to be taught in the General Chemistry course, Chem 120A, that were possibly covered in their high school General Chemistry course. The results of their responses were to be compared to their responses in the post-test to determine which concepts struggled with most.

Chem 120A post-test

The same assessment was distributed at the end of the semester, after lecture, to determine how well the students understood the content. The results of the responses in the post-test were compared to the results of the pre-test to find the common misconceptions and to determine which concepts need to be covered in more detail.

Results

The questions in the pre and post assessments consisted of the following: molecular representations of acids and bases, titrations, the equivalence point. The first question asked the students to draw a particulate level picture of HBr, hydrobromic acid, in an aqueous solution and label the particles present. The correct answer to this question was a drawing of a completely dissociated solution with H^+ and Br^- ions (water molecules optional). The progress of students from the pre-assessment to the post-assessment is shown in Figure 1. In the pre-assessment, 14 students got this question wrong and, in the post-assessment, 4 students got this question wrong.

Figure 1. Progress of students from pre-assessment to post-assessment. Students were asked to draw a particulate level picture of HBr in an aqueous solution and label the particles. There were 14 students who answered this question incorrectly in the pre-test and only 4 who answered it incorrectly in the post-test.

The common misconception with this question was that students were drawing partially dissociated solutions with HBr , H^+ and Br^- . Drawings of this misconception are shown in Figure 2.

Correct Answer

Figure 2. Drawings of students' common misconception for question 1. The two drawings on the left are the common misconceptions while the drawing on the right is the correct answer. The difference between the two misconceptions is that the leftmost drawing shows a partially dissociated solution with H_2O molecules, which are optional and do not need to be drawn, while the drawing in the middle only shows the ions in a partially dissociated solution. Besides that difference, the two drawings are the same representation.

In question 2, students were asked to draw a particulate level picture of a strong acid (HCl) and a weak acid (HA) in an aqueous solution, and label the particles. Then, they were asked to describe the molecular difference between the two. This was a three part question. The first part consisted of drawing the strong acid, the second part consisted of drawing the weak acid, and the third part asked for the difference between the two solutions. The correct answers we were looking for were: a completely dissociated solution with H^+ and Cl^- ions for the strong acid, a partially dissociated solution with HA , H^+ , and A^- for the weak acid, and the molecular difference being that the strong acid completely dissociates in an aqueous solution while a weak acid only partially dissociates. The results for this question are shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Comparison of results of pre-test and post-test for question 2. When asked about the strong acid on a molecular level, 12 students did not answer the question incorrectly in the pre-test and that number decreased to 7 incorrect responses in the post-test. When asked about the strong acid on a molecular level, the results were the same for the pre-test and post-test with 7 students who answered the question incorrectly. The third part of question 2 had 11 incorrect responses in the pre-test and 8 incorrect responses in the post-test.

The common misconceptions for question 2 are shown in Table 1. The common misconception with the drawing for the strong acid is that students were drawing a partially dissociated solution and they were drawing H and Cl atoms instead of H^+ and Cl^- ions. The common misconception with the drawing for the weak acid is that students were drawing a fully dissociated solution or just drawing an A^- ion with water molecules. When it came to describing the difference between the two solutions, students had the concept backwards; they answered that the strong acid partially dissociated while the weak acid completely dissociates, so they flipped the answer.

Table 1. Common Misconceptions for Question 2

Question	Common Misconceptions
2a	HCl, H Cl
2b	H ₂ O A-, H ⁺ A-
2c	SA does not dissociate easily, weak acid fully dissociates in water

Question 3 asked students to describe what happens when a weak acid is in an aqueous environment. The correct answer we were looking for was that the weak acid partially dissociates into ions. It is important to look at the data for the amount of students who received partial credit and those who skipped this question. In the pre-test, 4 students received partial credit and that number increased to 8 students who received partial credit in the post-test. Four students skipped this question in the pre-test while none skipped it in the post-test.

Table 2. Results for Question 3

Question 3	Incorrect	Partial Credit	Skipped	Correct
Pre-test	8	4	4	8
Post-test	6	8	0	10

In question 4, students were asked to draw a molecular representation of a weak base (B) reacting with a strong acid (HCl). The correct answer to this question was a solution for H₃O⁺ with HA, which results from reacting the weak base and strong acid. The results for question 4 are shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Progress of students from the pre-test to the post-test for question 4. All 24 students answered this question incorrectly in the pre-test and 23 students answered it incorrectly in the post-test.

Illustrations of students' common misconceptions for question 4 are shown in Figure 5. One common misconception was that students were drawing HCl molecules with a B^+ ion. Another common misconception was that students were drawing a completely dissociated solution with H^+ , Cl^- , and B^+ ions.

Figure 5. Common misconceptions for question 4. Students were drawing HCl molecules with B^+ ions or a completely dissociated solution with H^+ , Cl^- , and B^+ ions.

Question 5 was a two-part question. In question 5a, students were asked to describe what happens before the equivalence point during a weak base with strong acid titration. The correct answer for this question was that there are more moles of base than moles of acid present in the solution. In question 5b, students were asked to describe what happens during the equivalence point during a weak acid with strong base titration. The correct answer to question 5b was that there is the same amount of moles of acid as there is moles of base.

Figure 6. Comparison of incorrect responses and partial credit for question 5. In question 5a (left), the number of incorrect responses decreased from 10 to 4 from the pre-test to the post-test. The number of students who received partial credit for this question decreased from 8 to 6. In question 5b, the number of incorrect responses decreased from 10 to 6 from the pre-test to the post-test. Seven students received partial credit for this question in both the pre-test and the post-test.

Discussion

The progress from the pre-assessment to the post-assessment was probed along with the common misconceptions among the students. Question 1 asked students to draw a molecular level diagram of HBr in an aqueous solution and label the particles. Figure 1 shows a decrease in the number of incorrect responses from the pre-test to the post-test for this question. The number of incorrect responses decreased from 14 in the pre-assessment to only 4 in the post-assessment, which shows that progress was made in this topic. As shown in Figure 2, the correct answer for this question is a drawing of a completely dissociated solution with H^+ and Br^- ions, but the common misconception that students were drawing was a partially dissociated solution with H^+ and Br^- along with some HBr. This shows that students did not know that the H_2O molecules are what allows for the complete dissociation of HBr.

Question 2 was a three-part question asking students to draw a particulate level diagram of a strong acid (2a), a weak acid (2b), and to describe the molecular difference between the two (2c). For part 2a, the number of incorrect responses from the pre-test to the post-test decreased from 12 to 7 (Figure 3). This shows that progress was made in terms of understanding how a

strong acid looks in an aqueous solution on a molecular level. For part 2b, we see any progress since the number of incorrect responses stayed the same, at 7 incorrect responses, which means that more time should be spent teaching how a weak acid in an aqueous solution looks on a molecular level. Progress was made in terms of explaining the molecular difference between the strong acid and weak acid since the number of incorrect responses decreased from 11 in the pre-test to 8 in the post-test. Table 1 shows the common misconceptions for this question and the most important misconception to note is that of part 2c. In this question, the incorrect responses were the common statement of, “the strong acid partially dissociates while the weak acid fully dissociates.” This is the correct answer, but flipped. This shows that students seemed to have an understanding of this concept, but had the idea flipped.

In question 3, students were asked to describe what happens when a weak acid is in an aqueous environment. The correct answer we were looking for was along the lines of the following statement: the weak acid partially dissociates. Four students skipped this question in the pre-test (Table 2), which implies that they did not know this concept coming into the class and did not feel confident enough to attempt it. Although, none of the students skipped this question in the post-test (Table 2), which means that they were familiar with this topic and felt confident enough to attempt it. As shown in Table 2, four students received partial credit in the pre-test while 8 students received partial credit in the post-test. This shows improvement since students seem to have a better grasp of this topic.

Question 4 asked students to draw a molecular representation of a weak base reacting with a strong acid. This was the most significant question because no progress was made. As shown in Figure 4, all 24 students got this question wrong in the pre-test while only one person got it correct in the post-test. The common misconception with this question was that the solution should have HCl molecules and B^+ ions, or that the solution should have H^+ , Cl^- , and B^+ ions (Figure 5). Although, the correct answer was a solution consisting of H_3O^+ ions and HA. The reason that the students did not get this right could be because they did not know that the HA molecule results from reacting the weak base with the strong acid. This means that it was difficult for students to understand this concept and it should be covered in more detail during lecture.

Question 5 was a two-part question asking students about the equivalence point. Question 5a asked students to describe what happens *before* the equivalence point of a weak base and strong acid titration while question 5b asked them to describe what happens *during* the equivalence point of a weak acid and strong base titration. A lot of partial credit was given in these two questions because students were giving responses such as, “the acid and base would react” or “there are different amounts of acid and base” rather than stating more specifically whether there were more moles of acid or base. As shown in Figure 6, the number of incorrect responses in question 5a decreased from 10 in the pre-test to 4 in the post-test, which is a sign of improvement. The amount of partial credit given decreased from 8 in the pre-test to 6 in the post-test. Although, when looking back at the data, it seemed that the amount of partial credit decreased in the post-test because more students were answering this question correctly, which shows improvement as well. For question 5b, the number of incorrect responses decreased from 10 in the pre-test to 6 in the post-test, which shows that more students had a better understanding of this concept after lecture. The amount of partial credit stayed the same, with 7 students who

received partial credit in both the pre-test and the post-test. This shows that there were still students who had a grasp on the topic but did not understand it completely, which means that more time should be spent in the classroom explaining what happens *during* the equivalence point.

Implications

Research shows that having students work in groups on conceptual worksheets is a more effective teaching method than traditional teaching³. This is because students have to think about the solutions to the worksheets on their own instead of simply listening to the teacher without knowing which questions to ask. With this method, students can work together in groups and explain the material to each other, demonstrating to themselves as well whether they have learned the material. Concept mapping is another method that students have benefited from⁴. Concept maps are made by linking big ideas to their subtopics in a diagram, summarizing the ideas they have learned. The reason these diagrams are so successful in helping students grasp the concepts better because they allow students to make conceptual connections and integrate the ideas taught in class⁵. Research has also shown that scaffolding is a useful technique as well⁷. Scaffolding is an effective teaching strategy that is implemented by the professor. With this method, professors work through a problem step by step, slowly guiding the students to the correct answer. One teaching method alone will not benefit students, so it is important to implement a variety of strategies to engage the students and give them a more hands-on experience.

Conclusion

Overall, students struggled with drawing molecular level diagrams, especially those for weak acids and had difficulties with the equivalence point, in terms of explaining and depicting what happens during and after the equivalence point. It was determined that utilizing multiple teaching methods in the classroom helps students absorb the material better. There were some limitations in the research such as the fact that this was done in only one classroom of one instructor, so it is not as broad of a spectrum for the general chemistry course. Although, this research will continue with future general chemistry students. By putting together the data obtained over the years, certain patterns can be found among the students' responses to see if the misconceptions are prevalent.

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Appendix 1

Acid-Base Questionnaire – CHEM 120B

1. If you have the opportunity to look at hydrobromic acid with a very powerful magnifying glass, what would you see? In the following box, draw a particulate level picture of hydrobromic acid (HBr) in an aqueous solution that you would see. Label the particles present.

2. In the following boxes, draw a particulate level picture of a strong acid (HCl) and a weak acid (HA) in aqueous solution. Label the particles.

Strong Acid

Weak Acid

What is the molecular difference between them?

3. Describe what happens when a weak acid is in an aqueous environment.

4. In the following box, draw a molecular representation of a weak base (B) reacting with a strong acid (HCl).

5. Answer the following questions related to a weak base and strong acid titration

a. Describe what happens **before the equivalence point** during a weak base with strong acid titration.

b. Describe what happens **during the equivalence point** during a weak acid with strong base titration.